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Research Article

**CHARACTERISTICS ELECTROCARDIOGRAM CHANGES
AND THEIR OUTCOME IN PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH
CORONA VIRUS DISEASE****Madiha B, Rahid AK, Abidi ST, Yasmin R, Hussain H, Afsar A.**
Wah General Hospital**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) (severe acute respiratory syndrome not only affects the respiratory system but causes dysfunction of other organs as well.

Objective: *To assess the electrocardiographic (ECG) changes and their outcome during hospitalization of COVID-19 patients, not yet been comprehensively studied before.*

Study Design: *for 6months.*

Subject and Methods: *It is a cross sectional study in which diagnosed cases of corona virus disease confirmed by COVID 19 PCR test were included. There was no age and gender discrimination. Patients of any age, either gender were included in study. Data of about 100 patients was collected. Non probability consecutive sampling technique was used. Then nasopharyngeal swab sample was taken for COVID-19 PCR testing. ECG was done in order to look for characteristic changes. Outcome was measured in terms of 30 days' mortality.*

Results. *100 patients presenting with coronavirus disease were enrolled. The mean age of study patients was 46 ± 24 years ranging from 20 to 80 years. 70 % of male & 30 % of female. Death rate in male is 10% and female is 20%. 64% study patients having age more than 50 years, 36% patients having age less than 50 years. Highest death rate occurred in old age group and patients with ESRD and COPD.*

Conclusions: *Coronavirus disease is associated with different types of ECG abnormalities and associated with high mortality rate.*

Key Words: *COVID-19, Electrocardiography, Outcome*

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INTRODUCTION:

Coronavirus disease is an acute illness that involves respiratory system most of the times. Virus belongs to corona family, that comprises 43 types of viruses but only 7 types causing disease in human beings. Coronavirus disease for the first time appeared in December 2019 in Wuhan province China and spread all over the world.⁴ WHO has declared Corona virus disease as a global pandemic on March 11, 2020.⁵ In Pakistan first case of coronavirus disease is reported on March 27, 2020. Up till now there are around 200,000 confirmed cases and 6230 deaths has been reported in Pakistan.⁶ The overall incidence of coronavirus disease is around 24.4 million and 800,000 people died of this disease till August 28.⁷ In the United States, 5.8 million cases of COVID-19 have been confirmed till August 28, 2020 and 180,000 deaths.⁸

The major route of transmission is through respiratory droplets, respiratory secretions, saliva and through aerosol particles.⁹ No vertical transmission.¹⁰

This disease is equally distributed in children adults and old ages, however mortality rate is higher in old people, immuno-compromised patients, patients with renal failure, hepatic failure, and heart failure.¹¹

Coronavirus disease is characterized by release of cytokines. These cytokines further activate macrophages within the lung parenchyma; this phase is followed by immune dis-regulation.¹² Coronavirus has an incubation period of 3-14 days that may extend to 30 days.¹³ The presenting features are cough 49% fever 41%, shortness of breath 29%, tachycardia 42%,¹⁴ diarrhea 9% and low oxygen saturation < 92%.¹⁵ Covid-19 infection is prevented by social distancing, use of sanitizers, proper hand washing and using face masks.¹⁶

Indicator of sever coronavirus disease: Respiratory rate > 30 breaths/min, high grade fever for 5 days, poor mental state, metabolic acidosis, chest x-ray showing multiple infiltrates, plural effusion and consolidation.¹⁷ The hospitalization rate in confirmed cases is 14%, ICU admission: 2% and mortality: 5%.¹⁸

Cardiac involvement is common in COVID-19 disease. Myocarditis and cardiomyopathies are the common manifestations. Common ECG changes are cardiac arrest 1.3%, bradyarrhythmias 1.3% and 1.4% nonsustained VT,^{19,20} an ST-Segment Elevation in 2% patients²¹, left ventricular hypertrophy 33%, atrial fibrillation 26% and NSTEMI 3.9%.²¹

Corona virus disease can be detected by PCR. The sensitivity and specificity of PCR is 30-40% throat swab, 65% in Nasal swab. Many patients have elevated CRP, raised ESR and D-dimers.²²

Objective:

To determine the characteristics electrocardiogram changes and their outcome in patients presenting with coronavirus disease

Corona Virus disease:

Corona virus disease was diagnosed by PCR Test through nasopharyngeal swab.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

It was a cross sectional study. Sample size is calculated by using WHO (world health organization) sample size calculator where confidence level = 95%, Absolute precision 2.5%, Prevalence of COVID-19 disease. 4.7 %. Sample size 100 patients.

This study was conducted at department of medicine, cardiology in a tertiary care hospital. Duration was from 16th March to 15th September 2020. Non probability consecutive sampling was done.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients of both sex and age 20-80 years, diagnosed case of COVID-19 disease presented with cough, fever and shortness of breath were included.

Exclusion criteria:

Prior history Chronic Liver disease
Patients taking medications causing characteristic ECG changes.

Data collection procedure

Approval from hospital ethical committee is obtained before conducting the study. After telling the patients about the purpose of the study and taking informed consent, nasopharyngeal swab samples of all patients with documented COVID 19 symptoms were taken and sent to pathology laboratory of our hospital. PCR test for COVID-19 by ELISA kit method was performed. The report was collected by the studying doctor. The report was written on specifically designed proforma. ECG of all COVID-19 confirmed patients was done. ECG changes of patients were written on proforma. If the patients had severe ECG changes, patients were admitted in the hospital CCU and treated accordingly. The outcome was measured in terms of 30 days mortality.

Data analysis:

Data was analysed by using SPSS 26). Mean and standard deviation were used for quantitative

variables such as age. Frequency and percentages were used for qualitative variables such as gender, and ECG changes.

RESULTS:

In our study gender distribution of patients is 70% of male & 30% female. Death rate in male is 10%.

However death rate in females is 20%, the overall Death rate is 9%. Table1&2. Age distribution in our study is 36 patients had age below 50years and 64 had age above 50 years. Highest death rate in old age group. Table 1&3. According to co-morbidities, patients with ESRD and COPD are more prone to death. Table 4.

Table1. Baseline characteristics of patients (n = 100)

Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	Range (min-max)
		46 \pm 24 20 - 80
Agecategories (years)		
20-30	10	10%
31-40	08	8%
41-50	18	18%
51-60	28	28%
61-70	20	20%
> 70	16	16%
Gender		
Male	70	70%
Female	30	30%

Table 2. Study outcome according to gender distribution (n = 100)

Category	No of Patients	No of Deaths	%age of Patients
Male	70	07	10 %
Female	30	06	20 %
Total	100	13	13 %

Table 3. Outcome according to age (n = 100)

Age of patients	No of patients	No of Deaths	%age of patients
20-30	10	0	
31-40	08	01	12.5%
41-50	18	01	5.5%
51-60	28	02	7.1%
61-70	20	04	10%
>70	16	05	31.2%

Table4. ECG changes and Outcome (n = 100)

Diseases	No of patients	No of Deaths	%age of patients
1st AVB	01	0	0 %
LBBB	07	03	43 %
RBBB	36	0	0 %
LVH	07	02	29%
LAD	09	02	22 %
RAD	15	0	0 %
Prolong QT	02	01	50 %
ACS	01	01	100 %
RVH	11	0	0
Atrial Arrhythmias	04	01	25%
Ventricular Arrhythmias	07	03	43%

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of arrhythmias and conduction system disease in patients with COVID-19 varies from person to person. There is large number of reason to develop ECG changes in patients with COVID-19 disease. Hypoxia and electrolyte abnormalities are known to be frequently reported in the acute phase of severe COVID-19 illness.²³ In a study by **Chung** and his colleagues showed that, 10 patients (7.3%) were presented with palpitations. COVID-19-related arrhythmias were reported in 44% patients.²⁴ In our study, 3 out of 7 (43%) had ventricular arrhythmias, 1 out of 4 (25%) had atrial arrhythmias. A case reported by **Boi et al.** and his colleagues, a 66-year female, diagnosed COVID-19 by PCR test. The ECG showed sinus rhythm with a first-degree atrioventricular block (AVB), sinus tachycardia with SITIIIQIII, Mobitz type I AVB and atrioventricular junctional escape beat were seen. ²⁵ In our study, 01 patients had 1st AVB, No patient had sinus tachycardia with SITIIIQIII.

However the majority of patients presenting with a systemic illness consistent with COVID-19 will not have any symptoms or signs. 6.1% had prolonged QTc >500 ms,²⁶ 17.7% had atrial arrhythmias. 5.9% had ventricular tachyarrhythmias. In our study, 43% had ventricular arrhythmias, 25% had atrial arrhythmias and 50% patients had Prolong QT interval. Richardson et al. from the Lombardi region of Italy showed 60% patients died of cardiac arrest during 2020 COVID-19 pandemic however no cardiac arrest found in our study. Many factors contributing it stress due to pandemic, or delayed treatment.²⁶

In a single-center U.S. study of 700 patients with COVID-19, Chorin et al. 1.3% had cardiac arrest, 1 patient had a torsades de pointes, NO cardiac arrest and torsade pontis in our study, 25 patients had atrial fibrillation however 1 patient in our study, and 10 had VT comparing to 3 in our study.¹⁹ Fan et al. showed that patients with severe pneumonia due to COVID-19, 90% had asystole, pulseless electrical activity was found in 4%. 13% survival to 30 days.²⁷ NO cardiac arrest and pulseless activity was found in our study.

The basic and advanced cardiac life support to COVID-19 patients should be given with standard guidelines. To deal with the suspected or confirmed COVID-19 patients the care giving person should wear the appropriate PPE before entering the room: gown, gloves, eye protection, and a respirator (eg, an N95 respirator,²⁸ facemasks are an acceptable alternative).²⁹ Acute cardiac injury (defined as abnormal troponin level) occurs in up to 20% of patients hospitalized for COVID-19 with acute

myocardial infarction, 100% patients had high troponin P and Troponin I levels and are the marker of poor prognosis.³⁰

A study done by **Baldi et al.** and his colleagues showed that, 30% of patients had ST-T abnormalities vs our study 100%, 33% had left ventricular hypertrophy, 26% of patients had atrial fibrillation similar to our study 25%.¹ patient pulmonary embolism, no patients had pulmonary embolism in our study.³¹

CONCLUSION:

Corona Virus disease is associated with different types of ECG abnormalities and associated with high mortality rate.

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